

The Alkaloids of *Rauwolfia Serpentina*, Benth. Part II. Studies in the Ajmaline Series.

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In the course of a discussion (Part I, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 9, 539) on the identity of rauwolfine, $C_{21}H_{26}O_2N_2$, m.p. about 160° , isolated from *Rauwolfia serpentina* by van Itallie and Steenhauer, (*Arch. Phar.*, 1932, 270, 313) with ajmaline, $C_{20}H_{26}O_2N_2$, m. p. $158-60^\circ$ (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 8, 667), the authors had noted the presence of N-Me and NH in ajmaline as forming an unaccountable contrast to rauwolfine, but admitted the possibility of the Dutch authors' formula for it, as there was evidence to show that ajmaline is not completely dehydrated at 100° and its analysis reported after dehydration at that temperature could also correspond to $C_{21}H_{26}O_2N_2, \frac{1}{2}H_2O$. A series of combustions, however, carried out since and controlled through microanalysis (particularly after complete dehydration at 200° , (cf. chart below) as well as the results of studies in the mutual relationship of ajmaline and its subsidiary alkaloids, lead the authors to the conclusion that original formula for ajmaline $C_{20}H_{26}O_2N_2$ should be retained.

Ajmaline		C.	H.	N.
		73.10	8.13*	8.40*
After drying to const. wt. at 150°	... Found	73.00	7.84*	8.52*
After heating at 200°	... Found	73.80	7.89*	8.56*
$C_{20}H_{26}O_2N_2$	... Itaq.	73.60	8.00	8.60
$C_{21}H_{26}O_2N_2$	... Req.	74.55	7.69	8.23
After drying at 100°	... Found	72.80	7.70	
		73.03	8.12	
		72.30	8.13*	8.40*
$C_{20}H_{26}O_2N_2 + \frac{1}{2}H_2O$	... Req.	72.61	7.70	8.10
$C_{21}H_{26}O_2N_2 + \frac{1}{2}H_2O$	... Req.	72.62	7.70	8.75
After long exposure to air	... Found	67.00	8.30	7.62
$C_{20}H_{26}O_2N_2 + 1\frac{1}{2}H_2O$	... Req.	66.86	7.91	8.21

The CH values noted for nitrosoajmaline in Part I (*loc. cit.*), agree much better with the C_{20} -formula (the N values being good for both). (Found: C, 67.7; H, 7.11, N, 11.5. $C_{20}H_{26}O_2N_2 \cdot NO$ requires C, 67.6; H, 7.00; N, 11.8; and $C_{21}H_{26}O_2N_2 \cdot NO$ requires C, 68.67; H, 6.91; N, 11.41 per cent). Also the C, H values for benzoylajmaline

* Indicates the values of microanalysis by Dr. Ing. A. Schoeller, Berlin.

(*loc. cit.*) tally more closely with the C_{20} -formula. (Found: C, 74.6, 74.5; H, 8.05, 8.09. $C_{20}H_{26}O_2N_2 \cdot CO \cdot C_6H_5$ requires C, 75.4; H, 7.00; and $C_{21}H_{26}O_2N_2 \cdot CO \cdot C_6H_5$ requires C, 75.8; H, 7.00 per cent).

It has been further shown that ajmaline takes up 2 atoms of bromine in the cold yielding a crystalline dibromo derivative, which indicates the presence of an olefine double bond in its molecule. It also forms a sulphonic acid, characterised through its salts, and a tri-nitro derivative. From the crystalline product obtained on heating ajmaline to 200° (*loc. cit.*), and provisionally named in its crude and undefined condition as pyroajmaline (shrinks 240° , m. p. 256°) it has been possible to isolate after repeated crystallisation from ethyl acetate some unchanged ajmaline (m. p. $158-60^\circ$) but mainly a product which melts at $265-66^\circ$, agreeing with ajmaline in its analysis, colour reactions and NH and N-Me groups, but differing from it in being diacidic in character. It thus appears that ajmaline crystallises from moist ethyl acetate with three molecules of water (*vide* H_2O value in freshly prepared and air-dried ajmaline, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 9, 539), of which it loses $1\frac{1}{2}$ mols. on long exposure to air, a little over 1 mol. at 100° , nearly the rest at 150° , but full dehydration of ajmaline takes place only at 200° , whereby it is partially isomerised. The same isomerised product, which it is proposed to call *isoajmaline*, was also obtained on boiling ajmaline with caustic potash, though not sufficiently pure for analysis. In view of the respective mono and diacidic character of ajmaline and *isoajmaline*, and considering the absence of any hydroxyl, methoxyl or methylene oxide groups in them, the two oxygen atoms in ajmaline could be provisionally accounted for as forming part of a labile betaine grouping and the formulae for ajmaline (I) (for which $RNH \cdot Me$ was suggested in the previous paper) and *isoajmaline* (II) represented respectively as:

This would also largely explain the tenacity with which the last $\frac{1}{2}$ mol. of water sticks on to ajmaline, in so far as betaines are known to give up a part of their water of crystallisation with difficulty.

A revision of the formulæ of ajmalinine and serpentine through micro-analysis of the hydrated and the completely dehydrated bases show that while the C,H values reported in the first communication on the subject (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 8, 667) fully agree with those of the macro-analysis, the substance in the macro N estimation apparently could not be completely combusted, and that both the bases contain 2 nitrogen atoms like ajmaline, their formulæ working out to $C_{20}H_{26}O_3N_2$ (M.W., 342) and $C_{20}H_{20}O_3N_2$ (M.W. 336) respectively instead of $C_{20}H_{23}O_4N$ (M.W. 341) and $C_{21}H_{23}O_4N$ (M.W. 353). The original Cl and Pt values remain good for the hydrochlorides and the chloroplatinates of the bases for the altered formulæ inspite of the large reduction in the molecular weight of serpentine, the Cl found (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 8, 667) being theoretical for the original and 0.4% too low for the altered formula and Pt (*loc. cit.*) 0.4% too high for the original and 0.56% too low for the altered formula. The formula for serpentine also has now been fixed through micro-analysis as $C_{20}H_{20}O_5N_2$.

Ajmalinine, as already reported, is tertiary, contains no N-Me but an OH (now also supported through the formation of a benzoyl derivative) and a methoxyl group. Its relation to ajmaline, keeping to the formula suggested for it above, could thus be tentatively indicated by the formulæ :

Ajmalinine.

Ajmaline.

corresponding in a measure to the structural difference between strychnine and methylstrychnine respectively :

On heating ajmalinine to 200° in an atmosphere of hydrogen it is partially degraded, the molten mass yielding back some ajmalinine and an optically inactive crystalline product answering to the formula $C_{13}H_{17}O_3N$ (m. p. 272° decomp.) and named as *apojmalinine*.

Serpentine which is tertiary in character and contains one OH and one OMe, differs from ajmaline in containing 6 atoms hydrogen less in its molecule. In so far as its 3 oxygen atoms are already accounted for through hydroxyl, methoxyl and the suggested betaine grouping and it also fails to give qualitative tests for a quinone nucleus, its colour may be considered as originating from its higher grade of unsaturation. It was originally suggested (Part I, *loc. cit.*) that serpentine might be a secondary base like ajmaline as it gave a precipitate with nitrous acid, but on isolation and crystallisation it gave an analysis corresponding to a nitrous acid salt. Serpentine contains one olefine double bond like ajmaline, but of the two bromine atoms taken up by it in the cold, one appears to be secondarily eliminated as HBr, which adds on to the basic N, whereby a crystalline bromoserpentine hydrobromide is obtained. On heating serpentine to 210° in an atmosphere of hydrogen it is partially isomerised like ajmaline, yielding a crystalline substance melting at 256° and differing from it in yielding a stable gold salt.

Serpentine appears to be a dioxidation product of serpentine, but it materially differs from it in being secondary in character as shown by its forming a nitroso derivative. Its active H contents could not be determined after Zerewitinoff owing to its sparing solubility in both amyl ether and pyridine but it definitely showed the presence of 1 OMe in its molecule and the absence of N-Me.

The red colouration given by nitric acid with the alkaloidal principle isolated from *Rauwolfia serpentina* by Warden and Bose (*Pharm. J.*, 23, iii, 101; "Pharmacographia Indica," Vol. III, Append., 173-76) led them to suggest its relationship to the strychnos alkaloids by calling it 'pseudo brucine.' This view found a further measure of support in van Itallie and Steenhauer's (*loc. cit.*) qualitative tests for ammonia, quinoline, carbazole and skatol in the zinc distillation product of their rauwolfine. It was partly on this basis that the Dutch authors supported their C₂₁-formula for rauwolfine suggesting its isomerism with tetrahydrostrychnine, C₂₁H₂₆O₂N₂. An important feature of variance with these suggestions is contained in the fact that the ajmaline series of alkaloids could not have more than 19 carbon atoms in their main structure as against 21 in the strychnine series. Considering, however, the formation of a monosulphonic acid, trinitro and dibromo derivatives of ajmaline and the probable presence of a betaine grouping in the whole series, it would not be surprising if the ring system of ajmaline should be similar in its main features to that of strychnine.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Ajmaline ($C_{20}H_{26}O_2N_2$).

isoAjmaline was obtained on repeated crystallisation of pyroajmaline (*loc. cit.*) from ethyl acetate. It melted at $265-66^\circ$ and in 0.508% absolute alcoholic solution it showed $[\alpha]_D^{25} = +72.8^\circ$ as against $+128^\circ$ of ajmaline hydrate. [Found: (after dehydration at 150° in an atmosphere of hydrogen), C, 73.54; H, 7.86; N, 8.56; (after dehydration at 100° in *vacuo* over P_2O_5), C, 73.50; H, 8.0; N, 8.42; (after drying in air at room temperature), C, 73.7; H, 7.95; N, 8.46 $C_{20}H_{26}O_2N_2$ requires C, 73.6; H, 8.0; N, 8.6 per cent]. Determination of OMe in *isoajmaline* after Zeisel gave a negative result, but 1 N-Me after Herzig and Meyer and 1 active H after Zerewitinoff were found to be present. (Found: Me, 4.0; H, 0.35; $C_{20}H_{26}O_2N_2$ requires for 1 N-Me and 1 active H, Me, 4.6; H, 0.30 per cent).

The *hydrochloride* in 0.4% solution in distilled water showed $[\alpha]_D^{25} = +98.7^\circ$. (Found: Cl, 17.5. $C_{20}H_{26}O_2N_2$, HCl requires Cl, 17.5 per cent).

The *chloroplatinate*, prepared by adding aqueous platinum chloride to a solution of the *iso*-base in dilute hydrochloric acid under ice cooling, formed a dirty yellow mass, which quickly turns brown and melts at $227-28^\circ$ (decomp.).

The *iso-picrate* was obtained as a bright yellow amorphous powder on adding an aqueous solution of picric acid to an aqueous solution of the *iso*-hydrochloride. It is soluble in warm water and alcohol and crystallises from the solvent in spindle shaped needles which shrink at 100° , soften at $150-60^\circ$ and slowly char from 180° to 200° .

Dibromoajmaline.—0.1684 G. of ajmaline dissolved in 2 c.c. of dry chloroform solution and titrated against bromine in dry chloroform solution with ice cooling, took up 0.10 g. bromine (calculated for one double bond, 0.085 g.). The titration was followed by means of potassium iodide starch paper. On evaporating off the solvent at room temperature and crystallising the residue from absolute alcohol the brominated product was obtained in long prismatic rods, which turn brown at 216° and melt at 230° (decomp.). It is soluble in ethyl acetate and dilute hydrobromic acid but insoluble in water. (Found: Br, 33.17. $C_{20}H_{26}O_2N_2Br_2$ requires Br, 33.05 per cent).

Trinitroajmaline.—To 0.3 g. of ajmaline in a test tube immersed in ice mixture were added a few drops of well cooled concentrated nitric acid, when the whole mass turned deep red in colour. On dilution with

ice-cold water a yellow amorphous powder was obtained, which failed to crystallise out from any of the solvents and melted at 288-58° (decomp.). [Found: C, 52·7; H, 5·45; N, 12·10. $C_{20}H_{26}O_2N_2(NO_2)_3$ requires C, 52·06; H, 5·20; N, 12·15 per cent].

Ajmaline monosulphonic acid.—0·4 G. of ajmaline with 1 c.c. of conc. sulphuric acid (96%, d 1·84) was heated at 100° for 10 minutes, the reaction mixture was well cooled and diluted with cold water (7 c.c.) when the sulphonated product separated out in clusters of prismatic rods (0·39 g.). It softens at 310° and melts at 319-20° (decomp.). It gives a blood red colouration with concentrated nitric acid, is difficultly soluble in water and nearly insoluble in alcohol. (Found: C, 58·6; H, 6·53; N, 6·34; S, 7·8. $C_{20}H_{25}O_2N_2 \cdot SO_3H$ requires C, 59·1; H, 6·4; N, 6·89; S, 7·88 per cent).

Ajmaline monoammonium sulphonate.—On passing gaseous ammonia into a suspension of ajmaline monosulphonic acid in alcohol a clear solution was obtained from which the ammonium salt precipitated out on addition of ether in prismatic rods and plates which shrink at 262°, melt at 319-20° (decomp.), and are difficultly soluble in water or alcohol.

Ajmaline barium sulphonate was obtained in clusters of prismatic needles (m. p. 322-24°, decomp.), when a concentrated aqueous solution of barium chloride was added to an aqueous solution of ajmaline monoammonium sulphonate. [Found: Ba, 13·7. $(C_{20}H_{24}O_2N_2SO_3)_2 \cdot Ba$ requires Ba, 14·50 per cent].

Calcium, sodium and potassium ajmaline sulphonates were also obtained in prismatic needles when concentrated aqueous solutions of the chlorides of the metals were added to the ammoniacal solution of ajmaline monoammonium sulphonate. Ajmaline potassium sulphonate melted at 304-10° but the calcium salt remained unmelted up to 370°.

Ajmalinine ($C_{20}H_{26}O_3N_2$).

Ajmalinine, $C_{20}H_{26}O_3N_2$.—Micro-analysis after dehydration at 140° in hydrogen atmosphere (Found: C, 70·0; 69·97; H, 7·46; 7·39; N, 7·83; 7·85. $C_{20}H_{26}O_3N_2$ requires C, 70·20; H, 7·60; N, 8·20 per cent.). Macro value (*J. Indian. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 8, 667) (after drying at 100°): C, 70·4; H, 7·1. Ajmalinine after dehydration at room temperature gave C, 64·49; H, 7·56; N, 7·21. $C_{20}H_{26}O_3N_2$, $1\frac{1}{2} H_2O$ requires C, 65·04; H, 7·86; N, 7·59 per cent. It showed an absence of N-Me after the method of Herzig and Meyer and presence of OMe after Zeisel. [Found: OMe, 8·80. $C_{20}H_{26}O_3N_2$

requires OMe (for 1 OMe) 9·06 per cent]. Its active H determination after complete dehydration at 140° in an atmosphere of hydrogen after Zerewitinoff in pyridine solution showed the presence of 1 active H. [Found: H, 0·35. $C_{20}H_{26}O_3N_2$ requires H (for 1 active H) 0·29 per cent].

Benzoylajmalinine was obtained through benzoyl chloride in pyridine solution as an amorphous powder which frothed up at 100° and melted at 140-50°. It was soluble in nearly all the organic solvents and failed to crystallise from any of them. (Found: C, 71·84; H, 6·60; N, 6·20. $C_{20}H_{25}O_3N_2 \cdot CO \cdot C_6H_5$ requires C, 72·65; H, 6·73; N, 6·28 per cent.). Active H was found absent after Zerewitinoff. Its hydrochloride and picrate, prepared from the components in ethereal solution, formed amorphous powders both melting at 220° (decomp.). The chloroplatinate of the benzoyl base prepared from the hydrochloride melted at 242-45° (decomp.).

Ajmalinine methiodide.—To a solution (0·4 g., 1 mol.) of ajmalinine in chloroform (3 c.c.), methyl iodide (0·2 g., 1·2 mols.) was added and the mixture left well corked for one hour at room temperature, when ajmalinine methiodide separated as a pasty mass which crystallised from absolute alcohol in elongated rods, melting at 233-34° (decomp.). It is soluble in alcohol and water. It showed the presence of 1 N-Me after the method of Herzig and Meyer [Found: Me, 3·0. $C_{20}H_{26}O_3N_2 \cdot CH_3I$ requires Me (for 1 NMe), 3·11 per cent. and 1 OMe after Zeisel. (Found: OMe₃, 6·7. $C_{20}H_{26}O_3N_2 \cdot CH_3I$ requires OMe (for 1 OMe), 6·4 per cent].

Effect of heat on ajmalinine: apoajmalinine.—On heating for 2 hours at 150° ajmalinine did not show any loss of weight but after 5 hours at 210° in hydrogen atmosphere it suffered a loss of 16·6%. The cream coloured substance, thereby obtained, could be separated into an ethyl acetate-soluble and an ethyl acetate-insoluble fraction. The former yielded back unaffected ajmalinine (m.p. 181-82°). On adding ethyl acetate to a solution of the ethyl acetate-insoluble fraction in methyl alcohol till turbidity, apoajmalinine crystallised out in rectangular plates which were optically inactive and melted at 270-72°. After dehydration at 150° in an atmosphere of hydrogen it gave C, 65·6; H, 7·46; N, 6·11. $C_{13}H_{17}O_3N$ requires C, 66·4; H, 7·20; N, 5·90 per cent. Its hydrochloride, prepared by adding the components in chloroform ether solution, melted at 243-44° (decomp.) and was soluble in alcohol and water. The picrate, obtained in a similar manner from the components, melted at 231-32°.

Serpentine ($C_{20}H_{20}O_3N_2$).

Serpentine.—Micro-analysis after dehydration at 150° in an atmosphere of hydrogen gave C, 71.16, 71.19; H, 5.69, 5.79; N, 8.06, 8.06. $C_{20}H_{20}O_3N_2$ requires C, 71.43; H, 5.95; N, 8.33 per cent. Micro-analysis after dehydration at room temperature (35°) gave C, 65.6; H, 6.28; N, 7.74. $C_{20}H_{20}O_3N_2$, $1\frac{1}{2}H_2O$ requires C, 66.10; H, 6.34; N, 7.71 per cent. The macro value after dehydration at 100° (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 7, 667): C, 71.93; H, 6.3 per cent. Its active H determination in pyridine solution (after drying the base at 150° in hydrogen atmosphere) after the method of Zerewitinoff showed the presence of 1 active H [Found: H, 0.26. $C_{20}H_{20}O_3N_2$ requires active H, (for 1 active H), 0.29 per cent]. It showed the absence of N-Me after the method of Herzig and Meyer.

Action of nitrous acid on serpentine: serpentine nitrite.—To a cooled solution of serpentine (1 mol., 0.34 g.) in 10% acetic acid a well cooled solution of sodium nitrite (1.5 mols., 0.1 g.) was slowly added and the reaction mixture was left for 4 hours at room temperature. The precipitate which separated was filtered and washed with a little water. It crystallised from absolute alcohol, alcohol-water, and alcohol-ether in cream coloured stars of needles which melted at 165.66° (decomp.). (Found: C, 62.38; H, 5.42; N, 10.30. $C_{20}H_{20}O_3N_2 \cdot HNO_2$ requires C, 62.67; H, 5.48; N, 11.0 per cent).

Serpentine methiodide.—To a solution of serpentine (1 mol.) in chloroform, methyl iodide (1.5 mols.) in chloroform was added with cooling, and the mixture left well corked at room temperature. The methiodide which slowly separated out was crystallised from alcohol-water, when it formed slender needles melting at 271.72° (decomp.). (Found: N, 5.28; I, 26.82. $C_{20}H_{20}O_3N_2 \cdot CH_3I$ requires N, 5.86; I, 26.55 per cent). It showed 1 N-Me after Herzig and Meyer and 1 OMe after Zeisel [Found: Me 2.50; OMe 6.57. $C_{20}H_{20}O_3N_2 \cdot CH_3I$ requires Me (for 1 N-Me), 3.18; and OMe (for 1 OMe), 6.48 per cent].

Bromoserpentine hydrobromide.—0.2058 G. in 2 c.c. of dry chloroform titrated against bromine in the cold took up 0.11 g. of bromine (calculated for 1 double bond 0.098 g.). Owing to the reddish colour of the solution the titration was followed by means of potassium iodide starch paper. The residue left on evaporating off the solvent at room temperature crystallised from absolute alcohol in pale yellow

needles, which were soluble in water, insoluble in ethyl acetate or ether and melted at 257-58° (decomp.). (Found: Br, 31.48. $C_{20}H_{19}O_3N_2Br \cdot HBr$ requires Br, 32.26 per cent).

Effect of heat on serpentine: isoserpentine.—Serpentine is very difficultly dehydrated at 100° in *vacuo* over P_2O_5 and took 50 hours to reach a constant weight at that temperature losing 11.05%. The dehydrated base melted at 185-86° and became dark red in colour but when rubbed with alcohol or water the bright yellow colour of the hydrate and the melting point 158° were restored. On drying at 140° in an atmosphere of hydrogen there was no further appreciable loss in weight. On heating serpentine at 210° for about half an hour in hydrogen atmosphere a brown mass was produced from which isoserpentine was obtained which crystallised from absolute alcohol in prismatic rods melting at 230-22° (decomp.). It is very sparingly soluble in chloroform and ether and in contrast to serpentine easily soluble in alcohol. On dehydration in an atmosphere of hydrogen at 140° it lost 11.72% ($2\frac{1}{2}$ mols. require 12.5%). [Found: (after dehydration at 100° in *vacuo* over P_2O_5): C, 69.05; H, 5.76. $C_{20}H_{20}O_3N_2 \cdot \frac{1}{2}H_2O$ requires C, 69.56, H, 6.09 per cent. (After dehydration at 140° in an atmosphere of hydrogen), N, 7.91. $C_{20}H_{20}O_3N_2$ requires N, 8.33 per cent].

The residue obtained on removal of the solvent from the mother liquors of isoserpentine formed a dark brown powder, which was easily soluble in chloroform and ethyl acetate, frothed up 120-22° and melted at 230-32° (decomp.). It thus appeared to be a mixture of affected serpentine and isoserpentine (Found: C, 70.64; H, 6.0; N, 8.45. $C_{20}H_{20}O_3N_2$ requires C, 71.43; H, 5.95; N, 8.33 per cent).

The *iso-hydrochloride* was obtained on cooling the concentrated solution of the *iso*-base in alcoholic hydrochloric acid as spindle shaped needles. On drying in *vacuo* over P_2O_5 at 100° it lost 5.5% and melted at 271.72°. It was soluble in alcohol and water and insoluble in 10% hydrochloric acid. It showed a rotation in 0.486% aqueous solution $[\alpha]_D^{25} = +168.08^\circ$. (Found: Cl, 9.53. $C_{20}H_{20}O_3N_2 \cdot HCl$ requires Cl, 9.53 per cent).

The *iso-chloroplatinate* was prepared by adding a 10% aqueous solution of platonic chloride to an alcoholic solution of the hydrochloride of the base with cooling, when the chloroplatinate was obtained in slender needles which melted at 248-49° (decomp.) [Found: Pt, 18.10. $(C_{20}H_{20}O_3N_2 \cdot HCl)_2 \cdot PtCl_4$ requires Pt, 18.46 per cent].

The *iso-aurichloride* was prepared by adding an aqueous solution of gold chloride to a well cooled alcoholic solution of the *iso*-hydrochloride. The precipitate thereby formed was filtered, washed with water and alcohol and finally with ether and dried in *vacuo* over P_2O_5 . The aurichloride, thus obtained, formed a buff coloured powder which softened at 174° and melted at $194-95^\circ$ (reddening). [Found; Au, 29.00. $(C_{20}H_{20}O_3N_2 \cdot HCl)AuCl_3$ requires Au, 29.84 per cent].

The *picrate* was obtained by adding ethereal picric acid to a methyl alcoholic solution of the *iso*-base and crystallising the sticky precipitate from dilute alcohol when it formed crowded clusters of needles. It crystallised in elongated prisms from absolute alcohol. It is soluble in alcohol and insoluble in water, reddens at 250° and melts at 263.64° (decomp.).

Serpentinine ($C_{20}H_{20}O_5N_2$).

Serpentinine ($C_{20}H_{20}O_5N_2$).—It crystallises from dilute alcohol with $1\frac{1}{2}$ mols of water, of which it gives up $\frac{1}{2}$ mol. at 100° and the remaining 1 mol. at 150° . [Found (after dehydration at 150°): C, 64.84, 64.96; H, 5.76, 5.47; N, 7.19; 7.21. $C_{20}H_{20}O_5N_2$ requires C, 65.0; H, 5.44; N, 7.61 per cent. (After dehydration at 100° in *vacuo* over P_2O_5): C, 62.61; H, 5.77. $C_{20}H_{20}O_5N_2$, 1 H_2O requires C, 62.18; H, 5.70 per cent. (After drying at room temperature): C, 61.36; H, 5.80; N, 6.80. $C_{20}H_{20}O_5N_2$, $1\frac{1}{2}$ H_2O requires C, 60.67; H, 5.82; N, 7.09 per cent] Its active H could not be determined owing to its sparing solubility in both amyl ether and pyridine; it showed the absence of N-Me and presence of 1 OMe. [Found: OMe, 7.90, 8.07. $C_{20}H_{20}O_5N_2$ requires OMe (for 1 OMe) 8.42 per cent]. *Serpentinine* hydrochloride, originally reported to be as an amorphous powder melting at $260-62^\circ$, could be crystallised from alcohol-ether in amber coloured spear-shaped rods, which melted at $271-72^\circ$ (decomp.). (Found: Cl, 8.60. $C_{20}H_{20}O_5N_2 \cdot HCl$ requires Cl, 8.78 per cent). and showed a rotation in 0.26% aqueous solution $[\alpha]_D^{25} = +166.98^\circ$. The *picrate* reported earlier as melting at $225-27^\circ$, crystallised from concentrated solutions of alcohol in silky prismatic rods and from methyl alcohol-ether in spear shaped rods melting at 263.64° (decomp.). The chloroplatinate prepared from the hydrochloride as already reported gave Pt, 17.70. $(C_{20}H_{20}O_5N_2 \cdot HCl)_2PtCl_4$ requires Pt, 17.04 per cent.

The *aurichloride* was obtained by adding 1% aqueous solution of gold chloride to a well cooled aqueous solution of the hydrochloride:

It forms a yellowish brown amorphous powder which is insoluble in water and melts at 194-95° (decomp.). [Found (in air-dried gold salt): Au, 27.5. ($C_{20}H_{20}O_5N_2 \cdot HCl$). $AuCl_3$ requires Au. 27.85 per cent].

The *hydrobromide* was obtained as a paste on treating the base with dilute hydrobromic acid, which crystallised from its solution in hot water in stars of needles melting at 271-72° (decomp.). It is difficultly soluble in cold water and alcohol.

The *hydroiodide* was obtained by adding a concentrated solution of potassium iodide to an aqueous solution of the hydrochloride as an amber coloured powder sparingly soluble in warm water and alcohol, m.p. 271-72° (decomp.).

Action of nitrous acid on serpentinine: nitrososerpentinine.—To a cooled solution of serpentinine (1 mol. 0.37 g.) in 10 c.c. acetic acid, a well cooled solution of sodium nitrite (1.5 mols. 0.1 g.) was slowly added with shaking when a cream yellow crystalline product separated out. After keeping the reaction mixture overnight at room temperature the precipitate was well washed with dilute acetic acid and then with water to remove any unreacted base and crystallised from dilute alcohol, when a hydrate of nitrososerpentinine was obtained in brooms of broad needles melting at 159-60°. Dried in *vacuo* at 100° over P_2O_5 it lost 5.67; $1\frac{1}{2} H_2O$ requires 6.4 per cent. [Found (after dehydration): C, 59.90; H, 5.44. $C_{20}H_{20}O_5N_2 \cdot NO$ requires C, 60.45; H 4.78 per cent. (Air-dried nitroso serpentinine): N, 9.6. $C_{20}H_{20}O_5N_2 \cdot NO$, $1\frac{1}{2} H_2O$ requires N, 9.95 per cent].